

Evaluating the Employment issues and the need for Training in the context of Organization Psychology

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ABSTRACT

The Volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous (VUCA) world has left us with loads of chaos and confusion. The entire mankind has been grappling under the pressure of the pandemic and the aftermath related to it. In this context, there is a paradigm shift in the economic scenario and the unpredictability is writ large in every sphere of life. The job markets have toppled down and there is a fear of many challenges thereafter. The changing dynamics of employment are quite heartening because there is a complete disconnect between the graduating students and the industry readiness. In other words, the current generation by and large are not equipped to take up the challenges of the job market. There are various studies that have shown today's employers are vocal about employment issues especially in terms of the much-needed "Soft Skills" apart from their domain area expertise. As listed in recent reports, the top 10 employability skills for undergraduates as identified by employers include oral and written communication, leadership, teamwork, conflict management, initiative, responsibility, decision making, problem-solving, and critical thinking skills ([Hart Research Associates, 2013](#); [Drummond and Rosenbluth, 2015](#)).

Research suggests that employability skills are highly valued and that many employers rank employability skills above degree designation or university reputation (Finch et al., 2012). Governments have taken note of this trend, too. In some cases, they insist that postsecondary funding be tied in part to preparing graduates for the workforce.

Purpose: *The paper explores the most pertinent employment issues present in academia in the current era and how to bridge the gap of the glaring issues through intervention-based training.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *Data was collected from respondents (Students) of B-schools, Universities to understand their perceptions of the job markets and the skill-based approach. Also, the data was collected from respondents from the industry to understand the employability skills required by the industry during the post-pandemic job market. Qualitative research was undertaken to understand the gap between the perspective of employers and the students. An extensive literature review was done to understand and identify the gaps and thus formulate certain interventions like campus to corporate training, industry-based curriculum, new norms behaviour, tools and techniques, and many other perspectives.*

Scope: *This paper is based on exploratory research and has a wide scope for future research implications.*

Key Words: *Employability issues, Training, Interventions, Academia Industry Interface, Industry Preparedness Program, Post Pandemic job market, Skillsets.*

1. INTRODUCTION:

The New norm has been a kind of shock and disbelief to mankind. The raging war on one side and the pandemic on the other side have been a kind of major setback to all and sundry. The paper tries to focus on the employability issues in the industry in these unprecedented times and also tries to understand how these issues can be addressed through intervention-based training and workshops. In the present context, the workforce has learned the art of work from home or the blended hybrid model of work. Meeting clients online, addressing challenges and other perspectives have become totally a newer version altogether.

Considering the new ecosystem how important is it to look into the employability issues looming large in the industry. The paradigm shift shows that the changing business world requires different repositories of competencies or employability skills to survive in the changing world. (Buheji, 2020a) OECD (2019) This research paper explores the much-needed competency and employability skills needed for a new normal/covid era. (Levenso.2020) The study is focused to understand the employment issues and the glaring concerns. The objective is to identify certain interventions which can be used to correct challenges and thus make the students ready for jobs. Various studies have shown that employment issues are mainly due to the rote education system. Thus the focus of skill building is lost in the long run.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW:

Defining employability skills

The ability of an individual to perform efficiently in the job market is termed as employability skills (Cole and Tibby, 2013) According to Yorke (2006) employability skills refers to the cluster of competency needed to perform a task allotted by the organization, thus benefiting the society and economy at large. Thus, to build the right competency the student should carry the right attitude. In the new norm, the online mode of education has created a different mindset among the student community. The lackadaisical approach and the callous way of taking things into stride have resulted in more challenges. Thus, the educational institutes have a huge responsibility of creating a competency-building attitude among the students.

Employment factors can be the generic competencies, key result areas, problem-solving skills, decision-making abilities, emotional agility, and other capabilities George (2011) This concept is widely practiced across the world and the focus is to prepare individuals for job readiness so that the future job market can have control of employability issues (Peeters et al. (2019) and Romgens et al. (2019)

The word employability competency in the new norm goes beyond the ability to get a job but also sustains in the turbulent times. Be it pandemic or epidemic. In the current times, the question of managing different challenges requires a whole lot of effort and these stem from the intrinsic traits and characteristics individuals carry. Be it cognitive skills or analytical skills. The two main aspects of employability are to ensure the students get a job primarily and secondly the ability to tackle the challenges at the workplace Levenson (2020) The importance of skill-building is not a buzzword anymore but the ability to perform a given task (DEST, 2006) Employability has become a major challenge in today's socio-economic context. Thus, the word "Competency" is made up of two-dimensional aspects, conceptual and operational. This consists of cognition, understanding, use of psycho-motor skills, behaviours, and attitudes (Delamare Le Deist and Winterton, 2005)

The New Norm

The word new normal has been seen over a period of two years after the outbreak of the pandemic. The existing scenario has turned worse at the outbreak of Covid, the entire learning being in the virtual mode has totally taken the learners by storm. This is a very new pattern of events an unusual situation that was not expected. For this reason, the new normal is going to be the reality henceforth and we have to equip the next generation with the life skills needed to survive. Covid-19 has shaped different lifestyles like never before in history. The- radical changes in terms of doing business, delivering services, the need to react, realize and reflect are the most important priority in the current era (Buheji, 2020b)

There is an urgency in the air to reshape and redefine the education system in a more skill-oriented direction. The need to focus on the methodology of delivering skill-based training is important. Thus, the need for researchers to identify various interventions that can help in bringing an outcome-based approach is the need of the hour.

The review of literature thus gives a summary of the research gap

Meister (2020) noted that the new norm would foresee a transition and flux of change in the speed and quality of training for remote workers. Thus the Corporate would certainly emphasize skilled workers who are capable of withstanding the impending crisis rather than a bunch of individuals who would simply have scores and CGPA's in their toolkit.

The recruitment process will be more aligned with behavioural interviews and competency mapping. The literature review signals the need for employability competence and identifies some of the frameworks that can be integrated (Romegens et al (2019) it is constantly evolving and changing with a focus on building employability skills for the current generation. Robinson and Garton (2009) employability mean the ability to be employable and get retained there for a longer period. The competency shortage has been referred to in various studies thus there is a gap between the output of the educational and human development systems and what the industry requires in the current scenario or the new norm.

Employability is highly linked to the workplace learning and thus the need for continuous improvement and progress through the usage of the right competencies is important (Van der Heijde) 2006 The Organization in the new normal would be more involved in shaping the skill sets of the individuals through right training and collaboration, Thus the educational institutions have a great role to play in training the youth focussing on the much-needed skill sets and employment competence. Producing knowledgeable graduates with good academic standards is the top agenda of any country planning to be stronger and compete economically. Thus, the skill India movement by the honourable prime minister Shri, Narendra Modi also is considered to be the concept of employability training. The concept of employability competency is not new but students especially in the generations-international journal of Human Resource studies ISSN 2162-3058 2020, vol 10, no 2242 have become more conscious of obtaining these competencies. Buheji (2020a) and DEST (2006) say that the existing competencies might not be enough in the emerging new world and there is an urgent need to bring a repository of skill sets. And

the onus of responsibility lies with the education institutes to mould and create the new managers.

The competency shortage would be a problem that is signalled by many studies indicating a vacuum and a gap between the output of the educational systems and the industry needs. Fugate et al. (2004) the ability to get a job simply does not rest on the credentials alone but on the competency required to gain a job. Therefore, what is meant by employability in this paper is the industry preparedness program to be of sessions to reach employability. e conducted on a consistent basis for the present generation to make them employable.

Clake (2008) refers to the challenges in the normal education and training due to the high unemployment that is expected in the new normal, there would be a series of challenges on educational institutes and the training institutions (ETI's) to clarify the total workshops and series. ETI's are supposed to identify the repository of skill sets and competencies needed, and form a cluster in the new norm. Understand the need and accordingly create employable youth through training and workshops.

The other issues would be to understand how and what the processes of the learning programs and employment competency-driven courses like business communication, managerial accounting, business analytics, etc. Forrier and Sels (2003) also point out the challenges the industry might face especially during the boom and bust of the economy like mitigating risk factors and re-establishing its position or fighting for its survival. However, currently, there is a surge in technology, and zoom learning has become the new norm in the industry and other educational institutes. There is a real-time need for industry-specific skills and domain area expertise besides understanding, and analysing generic and specific skill sets. (Buheji, 2020) Thus individuals with main competencies would be the ones with a good imagination, curiosity, creativity, and resilience would be preferred to be recruited.

Heyler and Lee (2014) refer to the need for skills sets to survive and sustain in the unpredictable and fuzzy world of changing dynamics of the business environment.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

1. This paper identifies the extensive literature review of employment issues and also, the paradigm shift in the employability skills and the job fitment factors of students during the pandemic era.
2. The existing literature and working papers across multiple disciplines also have filtered the list of anomalies and the research gap.
3. This integrative review is based on the existing frameworks of C.P. Snow, 1959 of two cultures) also, the Research Scholar has developed a model to identify a new body of knowledge apart from the recommendation.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

1. The cross-sectional study identifies the relation between Independent Variable and the Dependent variable thus, the independent variable is the presumed cause which is the employment issues and the Dependent variable is the employment training which is the observed effect. Thus, the research explores the interplay between COVID-induced changes in the education system and the learnability quotient of the students.
2. The research subjects were 20 students identified from a leading B-school in Bangalore and a bunch of seasoned industry professionals from a leading data science-oriented mid-sized MNC. They were interviewed through a Focus Group discussion using the ZOOM meeting.
3. The Research findings showed that;
 - Students are bored with online learning during these 18 months of virtual mode
 - The zoom fatigue has started to set in and the interest weans away. They are not aware of what is being taught
 - Anxiety and irritability occur due to too many assignments which is more or less redundant
 - On the contrary the industry experts felt of late the campus and corporate inductions had to be revamped to basics like "communication, written and Oral, building team dynamics, Problem-solving, and decision-making skills etc because the quality of students with higher soft skills are rarely found to be shortlisted. The need and the expectation gap are widening between the employers and the employees.
 - The experts were expressing the need for industry preparedness programs and campus to corporate connections to stop further damage in the educational institutes.

Proposed Two -Dimensional Model

The theoretical construct of C.P. Snow, 1959 on two cultures has been identified. The following framework can be analysed to know further:

ACADEMIA	INDUSTRY
Education is driven by an intellectual curiosity	Translational Research, commercialization, and profit-making

Now to build an effective partner there is a need to breach the wall that separates both, that is academia and the industry. Thus, creating more unemployable youth in the country. Researchers have already begun the investigation by showcasing the following inputs:

1. Industry-academia research collaboration
2. Mitigating the risk factors
3. Centre for research and training
4. Action research
5. behaviour research
6. Creating a Research instrument to measure the output of competencies needed
7. Prioritize social science
8. Implementing a solution-centric approach
9. Industry practitioner's effort to spread workshops on skill-building
10. Initiatives to bring a big difference
11. Create insights
12. Develop research agenda
13. Align university activities with industry needs

Problem Statement

How can the Corporate and Academia partner together?

The Following suggestions were chosen:

1. Updated curriculum: There is a constant need for educational institutions to revamp the curriculum according to the need of the industry. This is an exercise that should be considered by creating a board of subject matter experts and industry practitioners together. This brainstorming would be of great help to redesign the curriculum and can bring the best practices of the industry.
2. Industry academia connect through seminars, guest lectures, conferences, etc can also be yet another foray
3. Research orientation to understand the problem statements and bring a research aptitude among the academicians
4. Introducing the industry preparedness program or the campus to corporate connect to enhance the employability skills on a continual basis.

\Researcher's Contribution/Intervention based framework

Considering the base of the VUCA Model (Volatility, UncertaintyComplexity, and Ambiguity the new model is created.

Predictability

Knowledge

FIGURE: 1

1. **Volatility:** The predictability is high and the knowledge is high. Because the new norm is not stable. There is a lack of stability and the new norm needs high resilience and adaptability. The missing line between academia and industry is very clear in this phase.
2. **Uncertainty:** The predictability is low and the knowledge is high. The causes are not known as it is a phase of known to the unknown destinations.
3. **Ambiguity:** The phase refers to low knowledge and high predictability. It is a causal relationship that could be understood in academia and changes integrated during such times.
4. **Complexity:** This refers to the phase of high predictability and low knowledge. The talent management concept of producing employable graduates for industry consumption can be implemented here.

Discussion and Conclusion:

The above-discussed model can be used to build employability training and interventions in today's context of the VUCA world considering the two-dimensional axis of predictability and knowledge. This research showcases the employability competencies that can be built by academic leaders in the course of time. The framework also focuses on addressing the needs of the new norm.

The researchers call upon doing more research on what issues the employers demand. This also means that the so-called proposed employment competencies should be the focus of the educational institutes if they believe in placements. This is the source of motivation for policymakers, industry experts, educational leaders, and human resource facilitators. The framework can be used for in-depth study on how to build interventions that can create an outcome-based approach.

5. RESEARCH GAPS AND THE KEY FINDINGS:

The gap identified in the literature is classified under the following sections:

Field of applications: The study is focused on students from the B-school, it could be applicable to undergraduates and other students as well. And the PHILOSOPHY of research is interpretivism (qualitative in nature) the research was based on a focus group. There is a scope for positivism philosophy. This study could have been done through qualitative data collection techniques.

The methodology could also have been exploratory, experimental, or empirical using tools like statistical tools or data visualization tools. The shortcomings in the philosophical methodologies could be addressed. Also, there can be better analysis and interpretation applied in this study. The time constraint is yet another factor that is very critical.

The study could only capture the current state, based on the literature review. However, a testable hypothesis would have been FINER (Feasible, interesting, novel, ethical, relevant)

This paper was based on a descriptive review.

6. SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATION:

The world is still reeling under the different variants of Covid then the blended model will survive in the long run and the students should be agile for learning. The world is going to thrive on the sustainability model and learning is going to be more agile. Hence keeping the option of integrating academia and industry is the only way to address the employment issues. Thus, we may help in creating more employable youths in the country.

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